

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

POLITICAL CHALLENGES IN CONTEMPORARY EGYPTIAN LITERATURE

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Abstract

Alaa Al Aswany was born on May 26, 1957 in Cairo in a family of writers. His works have been translated into 30 languages. The article looks at the works of the well-known writer, and briefly discusses the novels "The Yacoubian Building" and "Chicago", which have brought him fame.

The article analyzes the political, social, economic, and religious slogans and ideas of these popular novels in comparison with the real slogans of the Egyptian Revolution of 2011.

Keywords: El Aswany, Egypt, Egyptian revolution, Arabic literature, Egyptian literature, Hosni Mubarak, Jacobian Palace.

The American political magazine "Foreign Policy" periodically publishes the list of The Top 100 Global Thinkers of the modern world, that is, the names of people who have influenced the thinking of humanity in a certain period of time. The rating of 2011 has surprised the public in a positive way. Accordingly, it is noteworthy that representatives of the Arab world occupy the first ranks in the list of "famous" geniuses of the planet [8]. According to the publication, the opinions, most importantly, courage and diverse views of those mentioned have supported the establishment of democracy in the Middle East. In 2011, in the rating of the top 100 modern global thinkers whose intellectual activity is more important and influential for humanity, Alaa Al Aswany, the founder of the political organization "Kifaya" ("Enough") in Egypt, the dentist and writer, who is also called "revolutionist", was ranked the first.

Along with Al Aswany, the figures of the Middle East are also at the top of the ranking for the same year: the former director of the IAEA, Mohammed El Baradei, the marketing director of Google in the Middle East and North Africa, the Egyptian activist Wael Ghonim, the reformers Rashid Ghannouchi from Tunisia, Mohammed Heyrat al-Shater from Egypt, Syrian activists Ali Farzat and Ratan Zaytunah, Yemeni activist, Nobel peace laureate Tawakkul Karman and others [9].

As for Al Aswany leading the rating, it can be called his deserved conquest. Thus, the author's novels "Jacobian Palace", published in 2002 and translated into more than 30 languages, as well as "Chicago", published in 2007, are a collection of political slogans in terms of plot and ideas, thoughts and dialogues of the heroes, remind the manifesto of the Egyptian revolution. And as can be seen from the chronology, the author uttered these slogans before the 2011 Egyptian revolution and the Tahrir speeches.

In general, the words "spontaneous" and "accidental" are not valid in revolutions. Today, the role of the mass media and the Internet world in the progress of revolutions is precisely exaggerated. However, the historical development of revolutions cannot be denied; revolutionary laws remain unchanged. In Egypt, it is

possible to see that the revolutionary conditions have started to ripen since the end of the 1990s, and have started to manifest themselves as an inflamed wound. Besides, these conditions are described in all their nakedness in the novels by Alaa Al Aswany: unemployment, bribery, official arbitrariness, political arrests, poverty, etc. It is because of these reasons that the protest rallies launched on January 25, 2011 in Cairo, Alexandria, as well as in other large cities of Egypt, and continued until February 25, finally led to the resignation of the government and President Hosni Mubarak, who was in power for 30 years.

As mentioned above, as the reasons for the revolution are presented as the concentration of power in the hands of the same political authority and person for 30 years, deprivation of democracy, free choice, other political and legal freedoms, bribery, official arbitrariness, poverty, low standard of living, housing problems, unemployment, structural-demographic problems and so forth. These factors are evaluated by global political commentators as factors reminiscent of the dynamite of the revolution.

During the wave of revolution that started in 2011, the slogans chanted in Tahrir Square, which is considered a symbol of freedom in Cairo, gradually turned into slogans and exclamations in the language of protesters in other major cities of the country. Depending on the nature of the pronounced demands, these slogans can be relatively classified into three groups. The first group of slogans can be characterized as political ones. These slogans can also be analyzed in two subgroups depending on the demands being stated:

a) in the protests that covered the country, Egyptians first of all demanded the resignation of Hosni Mubarak, who has been in power since 1981, and chanted slogans related to him and his family members:

"Mubarak, go away!", "Go to hell, Mubarak!", "Mubarak, Mubarak, the plane is waiting for you!", "Game over, Mubarak!", "You are a donkey, Mubarak!", "80 million people hate you!", "We don't need Mubarak!", "Mubarak, scoundrel, the blood of Egypt is more precious!", "Mubarak, coward and scoundrel!", "Where is your father now?" (Addressed to the son of Hosni Mubarak. Kh.A) and so forth [10].

According to this classification, if we try to compare the ideas, slogans and dialogues expressed in Al Aswany's novels, the following picture will emerge - the heroes of Al Aswany also want the change of power, the resignation of the president who has been in power for 30 years, and after his departure from office, they wanted the person elected as a result of democratic elections, instead of his son:

"We, the undersigned, Egyptian citizens living in Chicago, United States of America, are very concerned about the situation in our country, specifically poverty, unemployment, bribery, internal and external debts. We believe that our country deserves a democratic governance. We are sure that our people deserve justice and freedom. We take advantage of the Egyptian president's visit to the United States and demand:

- the state of emergency should be cancelled;
- democratic reforms should be held and civil liberties should be ensured;
- a public committee should be elected to prepare a new Constitution guaranteeing real democracy;
- the president should give up the post he has held for many years, the assignment of power to his son should be prohibited, and an opportunity should be created to hold free elections with the participation of international observers" [2, 146].

Later, the author says from the words of the hero: "If Egyptians go to the streets and demand the resignation of the president, it means that something has changed and it is no longer possible to live in the old way" [2, 130].

And the author, who stood in Tahrir Square for long days during the Egyptian revolution, expresses these thoughts as a citizen: "My participation in the 18-day demonstration in Tahrir Square was the greatest moment in my life. I was getting stronger every minute. Unquestionably, I was afraid for my life while I was on the square. No one had any idea on what criteria the snipers who were there during the rallies chose a person in the crowd as a victim. For the first time, on January 28, a man was shot near me, standing a few meters away from me, and I saw how he died. It was dreadful, but at the same time, the crowd was not going to back down. The people stayed in the square and carried the general feeling of fear and overcame it. I have used the word "people" many times. But for the first time in Tahrir Square, I understood what this word really meant. Then I was sure that the revolution would conquer. If a ruler starts killing own citizens, then he can no longer stay in power" [3].

Consequently, as can be seen from these quotes, Al Aswany already voiced the demand for the president's resignation in his works long before the Egyptian revolution.

b) the slogans in the second subgroup are characterized by political motives such as democracy, freedom of speech, free elections, elimination of bribery, an end to illegal arrests and torture: "Egyptian, give up everything, except the revolution!", "Get away, Al-Adli, Minister of Tortures!", "Police, leave Egypt!", "Wake up, Arab people!" and so on [10].

We can find the demands and slogans classified in this subgroup by the heroes of Al Aswany: "This government, which calls itself democratic, falsifies elections and arrests and tortures innocent people in order to retain power..." [1, 43-44]; or: "Our country is a big country, it has been invaded for many years. Our people have great opportunities. And if we achieve democracy, it won't take even ten years for us to become a strong developed state" [2, 51]; or: "Egypt is ruled by an unjust and corrupt regime. All Egyptians - both Muslims and Copts - suffer from it... All Egyptians who are not part of the ruling party are discriminated [2, 73]; or: "Free the arrested!", "Stop the torture!", "Stop the arbitrariness!", "Egyptians want democracy!" [2, 192].

These quotes once again confirm that the slogans of the 2011 Egyptian revolution can be considered the successor of Al Aswany's novels.

In the second group, slogans of this nature can be called socio-economic slogans, as motives such as eliminating illiteracy, ending discrimination and injustice, abolishing unemployment, and increasing wages are voiced. The slogans "Bread, liberty, justice" [7], "Maximum salary" [5], which were more memorized during the Egyptian revolution, are already considered to be engraved in recent Egyptian history. When talking about socio-economic requirements in Al Aswany's novels, there is no need to specify it with explicit quotes. Thus, it is enough to emphasize that these slogans cover the main plot line of both novels of the author (1; 2).

During the Egyptian revolution, the religious groups opposing the regime in the country, mainly the slogans voiced by the religious organization "Ikhwanul Muslim", can be summarized in the third group. From the very first days of the revolutionary unrest in 2011, in addition to political, economic, and social slogans, the painted slogans written on the walls and those raised on the squares were also found: "No to the West, No to the East!" "Yes to Islam!", "A Muslim cannot be killed by the hands of a Muslim!", "By God, we will die, but we will not be fodder in the hands of the enemy!", "We will never be a toy for America!", "God is great!", "Islam!" and so on [10].

As for the slogans of the last group, i.e., religious groups, mainly stated by "Ikhwanul Muslimin", Al Aswany expressed this trend more vividly in his novel "Jacobian Palace". In the novel, dialogues, opinions of young people who joined the "Ikhwanul Muslimin" organization, the jihad movement, and the sermons given by the sheikhs are almost rich with slogans of this nature.

The political undertones in Al Aswany's novels can be enumerated in this way. This characteristic aspect has not been neglected by the Arab world, world political commentators, or "Foreign Policy" magazine. And Alaa El Aswany was rightly called the spiritual inspirer of the Egyptian revolution, occupying the first place in the magazine's 2011 ranking [8].

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